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**EXPLORING THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS
IN PEACE GOVERNANCE IN THE ASEAN:
THE CASE OF A GERMAN POLITICAL FOUNDATION
IN THE PHILIPPINES**

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20 July 2023

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled **EXPLORING THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS IN PEACE GOVERNANCE IN THE ASEAN: THE CASE OF A GERMAN POLITICAL FOUNDATION IN THE PHILIPPINES** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of ASEAN Studies.

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She grew up in Germany and attended her primary and secondary studies at the John F. Kennedy German-American School in Berlin. She speaks fluent Filipino, English and German.

Dedication

I dedicate this work to the Lord Almighty who has been my source of strength, grace and wisdom, through whose Grace and Favor I have been able to run my course and scale through the hurdles of my academic pursuit.

To my parents Ronaldo and Monica May, who planted the seed of knowledge in my mind and nurtured it.

To my grandmother Tarciana, who never stopped believing in me. To my grandparents Antonio, Nomar and Rosario, who left us too soon and are now at peace with our Creator, you will always be loved and remembered.

To my one and only sister, Anne Monique, my best friend, my confidante, you have no idea how you've inspired me to pursue my further studies.

To my husband, Sherwin who consistently pushes me to reach for the stars and has walked every step of this journey with me.

To my daughter, Sophia Rose, who fills my heart with happiness each and every day; and my son, who as I now write is playfully kicking in my womb, you both are God's greatest blessings and have been my inspiration to finish this work.

Lastly, to my dear self, for every moment that brought me to this point. For showing up, pushing through, and finishing what I started.

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Abstract

The study intends to narrow in the ASEAN-Germany relationship by focusing on the work of a German political foundation that supports one of the ASEAN member states in maintaining peace in the region. The research will present a case study concentrated on peace governance in the Philippines through the work of the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) and its partner civil society organizations. The KAS has been in the Philippines since 1964, and its work has focused on social market economy, institutional and political reform, and peace and development in Mindanao. To enable them to implement their work, the KAS cooperates with governmental and academic institutions, civil society organizations, and various stakeholders in the country. The KAS is an external actor towards which the ASEAN could possibly derive potential post-conflict reconstruction and peacebuilding approaches. It could share its best practices with other member states that experience the same conflict in their respective territories. Therefore, the peace in the Philippines does not only benefit the country itself, but also towards the whole peace and welfare of the ASEAN Community. Therefore, it is vital to research into different forms of cooperation with external entities to be able to learn and apply diverse approaches to peace governance in the individual concerned ASEAN member states.

The core focus of the research was to discover how KAS Philippines has contributed to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN. In the area of peace and development in the Philippines, KAS worked directly with its long-term institutional partner, the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG).

IAG plays an essential role as KAS' local partner because it enabled the latter to work with various civil society organizations in Mindanao. The study looked at the partnership of KAS with IAG to enable the assessment of KAS' work with CSOs in its mutual effort towards peace and development in Mindanao. The capacity building activities implemented consists of civic and political education, dialogue forums, training of civil society leaders and study tours. Their joint cooperation illustrates that their work has not only resulted in peace governance in Mindanao, but has also served as the Philippines' contribution to peace in the ASEAN.

The study used a qualitative research design. It was a case study on peace governance in the Philippines, and how the role of a political foundation in ASEAN member countries, such as the Philippines, aids in achieving peace in their respective territories. The chosen foundation is the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) Philippines Office. Three projects/programs were highlighted in the study towards which KAS have different partnerships with. A face-to-face interview with the current KAS Philippines country director was conducted, while the questionnaire method for the previous KAS country director was followed. Initially, face-to face interviews or the questionnaire method depending on the availability of the heads of the respective organizations were scheduled. However, due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 and the implementation of the nationwide lockdown, the researcher was not able to proceed as planned and only three out of the ten civil society organizations responded to the questionnaires sent. Nonetheless, the gathered data is deemed sufficient to address the goals and objectives of the study.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

The first chapter aims to establish a detailed background of the study. It encompasses the statement of the problem and its objectives, the definition of terms as well as the significance of the research conducted.

A. Background of the Study

Peace is the ability to resolve conflicts without violence and to work harmoniously with one another in refining the quality of living. International Alert (n.d.) has set five aspects of attaining peace: 1) it is when everyone has the power to participate in shaping political decisions, alongside the government is accountable to the people; 2) everyone has an equal opportunity to work and make a living; 3) everyone is equal before the law; 4) everyone lives in safety; and lastly, 5) everyone has fair and equal access to basic needs. Given the said factors, peace within and among nations is an essential concern that profits the welfare of all. Peace cannot be achieved by individual efforts of a nation alone, but rather through collective efforts with neighboring countries within the region, civil society organizations, or with international political foundations.

In the case of the ASEAN, amity among its member countries is not sufficient, but rather peace within the individual nations itself. The pacification of internal disputes is deemed necessary to enable a state to properly deal with any sort of conflict it would face in the international arena. The situation in southern Philippines and southern

Thailand is a suitable example, wherein their governments, civil society organizations and various stakeholders have sought various ways of ensuring peace. Both countries are home to Muslim minorities that have been engaged in persistent conflict with their governments because of their political objective of creating their own independent territorial state (Liow, 2006). In the past years, both the southern territories of Thailand and the Philippines have experienced separatist agitation and armed insurgencies as a result of their resistance to being assimilated into their nation-state's existing structure. As a result, religious nationalism resonates with the perceived illegitimacy of the central state and marginalization in the course of history (Nishi, 2020). The armed secessionist struggles by Muslim minorities have primarily been ethno-nationalist in character, but the impact of post 9/11 events on Muslim worldviews and has caused concern for Islamic terrorism not only in their respective countries but globally as well. The conflicts experienced by the Muslims in Mindanao and Malay-Muslims in Thailand are one of the many peace issues that have yet to be resolved by the ASEAN to thoroughly secure peace in the region. Hence, it is against this backdrop that the intended study is being pursued. The research aims to highlight peace governance in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) by examining it through the engagement of the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung Philippines (KAS) with Philippine-based civil society organizations in Mindanao. The study was examined through the peace and development frameworks and paradigms implemented by these entities. The researcher deems the significance of peace in Mindanao as a vital contribution of the Philippines towards sustainable peace in the ASEAN. In order to understand the purpose of the study, it is significant to commence by taking into consideration the reason for the creation of the ASEAN, the undertakings it has accomplished to maintain peace after its establishment in 1967, and its initiatives for

peace and engagement together with civil society organizations and foreign political foundations.

The establishment of the ASEAN. The Association was established based on the strong desire to settle peace, build consensus, and promote stability through regional cooperation and integration (Chareonwongsak, n.d.). The desire to achieve regional cooperation served as a pillar of aspiration for the five founding fathers of the ASEAN in its creation on 08 August 1967. Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore and Thailand, with the exception of the latter, were colonial states that have recently attained political liberation from centuries of foreign occupation. According to Ayoob (1995), these countries faced tremendous internal political instability, i.e. they were encouraged to launch a regional organization that can serve as an alternative ethnic conflict, unity problem, and weak security and defense system. Hence, this is specifically for regional peace foundations (Singh, 1995). These struggles can be attributed as an aftermath of the Second World War. The political structure in the global arena was dominated by the rivalry between the two superpowers: the United States and the Soviet Union. As a result of the conflict, Southeast Asian nations were obliged to adapt to the existing difficulties during the post-war period to ensure national security in the region. Furthermore, Severino (1999) emphasizes that the realization of a regional organization could fill the power vacuum left by the major powers, provide a self-help mechanism for the newly-independent countries, i.e., enabling them to concentrate on nation-building and economic development and provide more weight to their collective voice in the international community.

The ASEAN did not simply emerge in 1967. A series of pre-organizations transpired in the process of its conception:

The Southeast Asia Treaty Organization (SEATO) can be considered as the initial organization formed. SEATO consisted of only two Southeast Asian countries. It was signed in 1954 by the representatives of Australia, France, New Zealand, Pakistan, the Philippines, Thailand, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The SEATO was intended to ally the different former colonies of Southeast Asia into one cohesive bloc with the aim of curbing communist expansion (Gentilucci, 2015). The SEATO was modelled along the lines of NATO, but it failed to distinguish the needs of Southeast Asia from the needs of Europe that led to its decline in 1977 (Gentilucci, 2015).

The Southeast Asia Friendship and Economic Treaty (SEAFAT) between Malaya and the Philippines, established in 1959, was the second attempt to establish cooperation. Its objective was limited to economy, trade, and education (Keling, et. al, 2011). However, the clashes among several Southeast Asian led to its abolishment.

A third attempt was the Association of Southeast Asia (ASA) established in 1961. ASA consisted of Malaya, the Philippines, and Thailand. Among its goals were to create peace and regional stability, cultivate cooperation in the field of economic, social science and culture, as well as to provide social justice and economic well-being (Keling, et. al, 2011 and Mahiwo, n.d.). Yet again, the cooperation failed due to territorial disputes among the three member countries.

The alliance between Malaysia, the Philippines and Indonesia, known as the MAPHILINDO, was the fourth attempt in attaining regional cooperation in 1963. It aimed at creating collaboration in the field of economy, culture and social science, and to serve as a key to end the territorial conflicts between Malaysia, Indonesia, and the Philippines (Keling, et. al, 2011). Unfortunately, this attempt did not succeed due to the Konfrontasi between Indonesia and Malaysia that lasted from 1963 to 1966. Furthermore, Wey (2016) claims that the end of the Konfrontasi led to the formation of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) on 08 August 1967.

Alongside the decline of the MAPHILINDO and prior to the birth of the ASEAN, a fifth regional cooperation known as the Asian and Pacific Council (ASPAC) was recognized in 1966. This consisted of four Southeast Asian countries, namely, Malaysia, the Philippines, Thailand and South Vietnam, together with Australia, New Zealand, Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. It aimed to bring together non-communist states to hinder external threats and provide a framework for more widespread cooperation (Tongzon, 2009). Unfortunately, the cooperation failed in 1975 due to tensions in international politics.

The creation of the ASEAN in 1967 was the first prosperous attempt in attaining regional economic cooperation. Since then, the ASEAN has opened its doors to the remaining five Southeast Asian states: Brunei in 1984, Vietnam in 1995, Laos and Myanmar in 1999, and Cambodia in 1997.

The concrete realization of forming regional economic cooperation was indeed not an easy task for the newly-independent Southeast Asian nations. First and

foremost, they consist of diverse colonial backgrounds. Given this condition, there is difficulty in the decision-making process among the countries due to their opposing political views. Second, they were still in an early stage of developing their own political, social, and economic stability in their respective nations. Hence, collaboration with other nations requires double effort of building both internal and external structures. Third, they were in a phase where they still lacked confidence and trust with one another due to their fear of experiencing foreign domination. Therefore, a lack in membership in the various organizations hinders the growth and complete implementation of its objectives. The initiative of the pre-ASEAN organization to aim for regional economic cooperation was an indispensable key to the formation of the ASEAN. With that in mind, the pre-ASEAN organizations' setbacks gave rise to a successful alliance of Southeast Asian nations that has been striving to improve its political, social, and economic structure for the past 50 years.

Maintaining Peace since 1967. The ASEAN has created several formal agreements towards peace and stability in the Southeast Asian region. First, the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation in Southeast Asia, signed in 1976, constitutes a code of behavior for States of Southeast Asia. It is also a mechanism for the peaceful settlement of disputes through regional processes. Secondly, the Treaty on the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone, signed in 1995 and now in force, is ASEAN's contribution to the cause of the non-proliferation of nuclear weapons, as well as to the safety of the region. ASEAN is currently consulting with the five Nuclear Weapon States to enlist their support for the sanctity of the Southeast Asia Nuclear Weapons Free Zone. Third, ASEAN has worked in cooperation with China on a regional code of conduct in the South China Sea, where there are overlapping claims

of some ASEAN members and China. At the ASEAN-China Summit in Kuala Lumpur in December 1997, ASEAN and China reached a common understanding that the maintenance of regional peace and stability served the interests of all parties. The parties concerned in the South China Sea disputes agreed to resolve their disputes through friendly consultations and negotiations, in accordance with the universally recognized international law, including the 1982 UN Convention on the Law of the Sea, without resorting to the threat or use of force (ASEAN Secretariat, 2012).

At present, the most known international organization with which the ASEAN engages with is the United Nations. According to the ASEAN Secretariat (2012), the cooperation to promote regional and international peace, and security is a key feature of the ASEAN-UN Comprehensive Partnership. The UN has contributed to activities within ASEAN-led mechanisms, including the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF). Furthermore, the ASEAN-UN collaboration in peace-keeping, and post-conflict peace-building, continues to be strengthened through activities conducted in national focal points of ASEAN Member States, and the ASEAN Peacekeeping Centres Network (APCN) (ASEAN Secretariat, 2012). The ASEAN Member States have contributed approximately 5,500 military and police personnel, as well as technical expertise to the UN peace-keeping missions since July 2015. The United Nations intends to further develop the ASEAN's peace-keeping capacities through training programs, and exchanges on policies and best practices (ASEAN Secretariat, 2012).

Initiatives for peace and engagement with external bodies. The ASEAN member states, through the 2015 Kuala Lumpur Declaration, commit themselves towards the enhancement of their cooperation with their dialogue partners and

relevant external parties, particularly, within the framework of ASEAN-led mechanisms in all three pillars of the ASEAN Community. This would complement regional efforts to strengthen a people-oriented, people-centered, and rules-based ASEAN. Prior to the 2015 Declaration, the ASEAN Civil Society Conference/ASEAN Peoples' Forum (ACSC/APF) was also established in Kuala Lumpur in 2005. This served as the key forum for civil society engagement, with the ASEAN making peace and security in the region one of its priorities. Throughout its eleven years of engagement with ASEAN, the ACSC/APF has focused in organizing national consultations and workshops, national and regional meetings with government counterparts, regional consultative meetings, crafting the ACSC/APF annual statement, holding parallel conferences with the ASEAN Summit, mass mobilization, and an interface with ASEAN heads of state (Tadem, 2017).

Aside from the ASEAN's intention to work with civil society organizations within the region, it also goes into partnerships with foreign entities. One of the many foreign agreements it has entered into is the ASEAN-Germany Partnership.

Germany has been a development partner of the ASEAN, since July 24, 2016, during the 49th ASEAN Foreign Ministers' Meeting. As a result of its new role to the Association, the first ASEAN-Germany Development Partnership Committee Meeting which was held on January 23, 2017 at the ASEAN Secretariat led to the creation of the ASEAN-Germany Development Partnership. At present, the ASEAN-Germany Development Partnership 2018-2022, aims to implement future cooperation under the framework of the ASEAN-Germany Development Partnership. It also serves as a foundation for practical cooperation to further substantiate the partnership and

cooperation with a focus on practical areas for mutual benefits, where ASEAN and Germany have expertise and mutual interests (ASEAN Secretariat, 2019). Under their practical cooperation in the field of political-security, peace and reconciliation is one of the areas they intend to develop through programs, projects, or cooperative activities.

In line with the foregoing, the study intends to narrow in the ASEAN-Germany relationship by focusing on the work of a German political foundation that supports one of the ASEAN member states in maintaining peace in the region. The research will present a case study concentrated on peace governance in the Philippines through the work of the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) and its partner civil society organizations. The KAS has been in the Philippines since 1964, and its work has focused on social market economy, institutional and political reform, and peace and development in Mindanao. To enable them to implement their work, the KAS cooperates with governmental and academic institutions, civil society organizations, and various stakeholders in the country. The KAS is an external actor towards which the ASEAN could possibly derive potential post-conflict reconstruction and peacebuilding approaches. It could share its best practices with other member states that experience the same conflict in their respective territories. Therefore, the peace in the Philippines does not only benefit the country itself, but also towards the whole peace and welfare of the ASEAN Community. Therefore, it is vital to research into different forms of cooperation with external entities to be able to learn and apply diverse approaches to peace governance in the individual concerned ASEAN member states.

B. Statement of the Problem and Objectives

Main Problem

How does the cooperation between Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) Philippines, the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG) and its partner civil society organizations contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN?

Specific Problems

1. What is the historical background, profile and goals of KAS since its establishment in the Philippines?

2. What are the individual roles of KAS, IAG and CSOs to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

3. What are the challenges encountered by KAS, IAG and CSOs to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

4. What can KAS Philippines and its partner CSOs recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Main Objective

To elaborate how KAS Philippines, IAG and its partner CSOs have contributed to peacebuilding efforts in Mindanao and Philippine efforts in ASEAN.

Specific Objectives

1. To define the historical background, profile and goals of KAS since its establishment in the Philippines.

2. To describe the roles of KAS, IAG and CSOs to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN

3. To determine the challenges encountered by KAS, IAG and its partner CSOs to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN.

4. To provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts.

C. Definition of Terms

Civil Society Organizations:

Non-State, not-for-profit, voluntary entities formed by people in the social sphere that are separate from the State and the market. CSOs represent a wide range of interests and ties. They can include community-based organizations, as well as non-governmental organizations (NGOs). In the context of the UN Guiding Principles

Reporting Framework, CSOs do not include business or for-profit associations (UNGP Reporting Framework, n.d.).

Governance:

Governance refers to “the exercise of authority to implement rules and policies in an effort to bring order to social, political, economic, and judicial processes that allows a society to develop” (Snodderly in Islam, 2018).

Peace:

Peace is defined in two senses: positive peace and negative peace. Positive peace refers to the absence of structural violence, which includes exploitation, hunger, malnutrition, and corruption on the other hand, negative peace is defined as the absence of direct violence like interstate war, civil war, and injury (Galtung in Islam, 2018).

Peace Building:

Peacebuilding involves a range of measures targeted to reduce the risk of lapsing or relapsing into conflict by strengthening national capacities at all levels for conflict management, and laying the foundations for sustainable peace and development. Peacebuilding strategies must be coherent and tailored to the specific needs of the country concerned, based on national ownership. It should comprise a carefully prioritized, sequenced, and a relatively narrow set of activities aimed at achieving the above objectives (UNDP in Alliance for Peacebuilding, 2013).

Peace Governance:

Governance systems that contribute to stable peace are characterized by having inclusive means of operating participatory systems that bring the governed into the process of decision making and systems for accountability that ensure transparent and equitable operations, and enough systemic capacity (Seyle, 2017).

Political Foundation / Politische Stiftung:

In Germany, it is a state-subsidized political foundation that is affiliated to a political party. There are six foundations at the federal level: one for each party represented in the federal parliament (Bundestag). They conduct party related work such as the spread of general information about their ideological cause, training of volunteers, publication of pamphlets and international aid for democracy building, in cooperation with their partners around the world (Kaiser & Starie, 2005).

D. Significance of the Study

This research study intends to focus on the role of KAS Philippines and its contribution to peace governance in the ASEAN, particularly, through their projects in Mindanao. The documentation of their various engagements in sustaining peace and promoting development in conflict-affected areas can guide in building a resilient, peaceful, and more stable ASEAN. The current development in the Bangsamoro not only sets the groundwork of security, inclusivity, and improvement in the region, but also brings more opportunities for the people of Mindanao, the Philippines, and the ASEAN community. Furthermore, the realization of the peace process contributes to

ASEAN's increasing knowledge and best practices in the advancement of a culture of peace and respect for diversity among its peoples.

E. Scope and Limitation

The study focused on the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) as the German political foundation. The KAS has eight (8) country offices in Southeast Asia, which are members of the ASEAN. However, the study focused on the work of KAS Philippines country office, with their respective partner organizations during the time period 2015 to 2020. The three projects of the KAS and its partner institution, included in the study are the following:

1. Democratic Party Development Bangsamoro (DEPAdev)

- Partner organization: Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)
- Project duration: 01 September 2015 to 28 February 2017

2. Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) – Phase 1

- Partner Organization: Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)
- Project duration: 1 March 2017 to 31 March 2018

3. Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) – Phase 2

- Partner Organization: Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)
- Project duration: 1 April 2018 – 31 March 2020

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The second chapter intends to present the review of related literature and the research gap in relation to the study conducted.

A. ASEAN Initiatives in ASEAN Peacebuilding. Peace and security have played a significant factor in the establishment of international and regional organizations after the Cold War. These newly created bodies have since functioned as an instrument to maintain peace in their respective territories. Hence, the study conducted by Karimi et. al. (2016) derives their hypothesis from these statements, by assuming that the ASEAN has had an effective role in peacebuilding and peacekeeping through creating norms and regimes of peaceful settlement of disputes and strengthening interdependency. The researchers managed to conduct their study by using the theories of interdependency and liberal institutionalism. The former believes in the advantage of free trade by maintaining peace since it draws states into a web of economic interdependence. This means that the material costs of international conflict are so vast that warfare becomes basically unthinkable (Keohane & Nye in Karimi et al., 2016). On the other hand, liberal institutionalism considers regimes to constrain and regularize the behavior of participants, affects which issues among protagonists move on and off agendas, determines which activities are legitimated or condemned, and influences whether, when, and how conflicts are resolved (Puchala & Hopkins in Karimi et al., 2016).

The researchers backed up their assumption by highlighting two important factors that would support their chosen theories: first, the interdependency of the Southeast Asian nations prior to and after the creation of the ASEAN in 1967; and second, the ASEAN's common identity and their norms of disputes settlement. For their first argument, a number of trade agreements have been mentioned that have led to the development of the ASEAN intra-region market. The trade liberalization process which includes reduction of tariff and trade facilitation has been a significant terrain in ASEAN regional economic cooperation (Guangsheng in Karimi et al., 2016). As a whole, the integration has created a peaceful, cooperative, and coordinative macro environment, which is definitely necessary for economic development (Karimi et al., 2016). For their second argument, the researchers have cited the set of norms for intra-regional relations, which are: (1) non-use of force and peaceful settlement disputes, (2) regional autonomy, (3) no military pacts and preference for bilateral defense cooperation, and (4) the doctrine of non-interference. As a result of these norms, the ASEAN has maintained the peace among its member nations.

In terms of the concrete action that the ASEAN has accomplished to fulfill its initiatives, the ASEAN has undertaken measures to aid their member countries in internal conflicts, such as (1) the ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Haze, which has been organized to mobilize regional and international support to help Indonesia cope with the forest fires in Sumatra and Kalimantan; and (2) the ASEAN Finance Ministers with support from the ADB and the World Bank, to undertake periodic "peer reviews" of one another's macroeconomic situations and policies (Severino, 2012).

In addition to the ASEAN's internal efforts, Rupprecht (2014) suggests that internationalization through involvement of third parties in mediating peace negotiations has shown positive effects on the resolution process of state-internal conflicts. He suggests that: (1) the ASEAN should explore its potential as regional actor in conflict management and should play a more significant role in managing conflicts within its own region in order to prevent the unilateral intervention by external powers; and (2) the OIC as another intergovernmental organization to stand as a role model due to its expertise in managing state-internal conflicts in Southeast Asia. As a whole, the non-traditional security issues that are linked to state-internal conflicts demand a more proactive role of ASEAN in the field of conflict management (Rupprecht, 2014).

B. ASEAN Body responsible for Peacebuilding. The ASEAN Institute for Peace and Reconciliation (AIPR) is responsible for the ASEAN's research activities on peace, conflict management, and conflict resolution. As outlined in its terms of reference (TORs), adopted by the ASEAN Foreign Ministers in 2012, AIPR is mandated to undertake a number of activities, including research, capacity-building, developing a pool of expertise, networking and information dissemination (Buensuceso, 2017).

Buensuceso (2017) elaborates AIPR's work as follows:

(1) In terms of research, AIPR compiles ASEAN experiences and best practices on peace, conflict management, and conflict resolution, as well as post-conflict

peacebuilding. These research activities are with a view to providing appropriate recommendations to ASEAN member states and bodies, at their request.

(2) In regard to capacity-building, AIPR holds workshops on peace, conflict management, and conflict resolution; on advancement of work in the area of interfaith dialogue; and on building knowledge among relevant government officials, scholars and think tanks.

(3) With respect to developing a pool of experts, it is envisioned that this pool would be tapped by ASEAN member states to serve as resource staff for conflict management and resolution activities, including providing policy recommendations on the promotion of peace and reconciliation.

(4) As for networking, AIPR is envisioned to serve as a knowledge hub, by establishing linkages with relevant institutions and organizations in ASEAN member states, as well as with similar organizations at the regional and international levels.

(5) Lastly, with regard to information dissemination, AIPR is expected to raise awareness and understanding of the topics within its ambit.

In addition, the role of the AIPR is inseparable from the framework of the ASEAN Political-Security Community (APSC) since the AIPR was established under a Provision (B.2.2.i) of the 1 March 2009 APSC Community Blueprint 2009-2015 (Buensuceso, 2017). As a whole, the work of the AIPR also complies with the promotion of activities under the APSC Blueprint.

C. Nature of German Political Foundations. The Federal Republic of Germany allocates government funds to six of its political foundations, linked to a political party that has been elected to seats in the German federal parliament for two consecutive terms. The following six foundations are currently existent: 1. the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung is allied by the Social Democrats, SPD, 2. the Friedrich-Naumann-Stiftung is allied by the Free Democrats, FDP, 3. the Hanns-Seidel-Stiftung is allied by the Bavarian Christian Democrats, CSU, 4. the Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung is allied by the Alliance 90/the Green Party, 5. the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung is allied by the Christian Democrats, CDU and 6. the Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung is allied by the Left Party.

The headquarters of the political foundations are mostly based in Berlin, with their satellite offices present in the other federal states, and their country offices visible in all parts of the global region. The underlying principles of the political foundations are to encourage civil society participation, grant scholarships to youth with academic capacities, and to spread democracy internationally. They are mandated by the federal government to deliver socio-political and democratic education; and to disseminate information and policy analysis both locally and internationally. In addition, they strive to promote liberal democracy ideologies and observe solidarity, subsidiarity, and tolerance in all their activities worldwide.

The foundations are able to implement their work in the designated country offices abroad by choosing institutional and contractual partners that fit to their underlying principles and advocacies. Unmüssig (2017) outlines how the foundations are able to spread their work: (1) they support scholarship and research as a basis for

political action; (2) they conduct historical research into the development of parties and political movements; (3) they prepare political analyses, empirical studies and informational material on a range of topics; (4) they work to preserve art and culture; (5) they award scholarships and grants to the youth; and (6) they support international development, based on the rule of law and democratic standard.

D. Research Gap

After having read several studies and articles on the work of internal actors, political foundations and peace governance in the ASEAN, the researcher believes that the existing literature is quite scarce. Most of the studies are about the role of civil society organizations in the individual ASEAN member states, but there is a dearth of studies on how they engage with foreign entities outside the ASEAN, and what specific projects and activities do they collaborate on to enhance their participation.

Chapter III

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The third chapter conveys both the theoretical and conceptual framework used for the research conducted.

A. Theoretical Framework

The research applied the 'theory of peace as freedom', which basically links both Johan Galtung's 'theory of peace' and Amartya Sen's 'theory of development'. By synthesizing Sen's development as freedom with Galtung's theory of peace, it leads to the definition of peace as the goal and process of expanding people's freedoms (Barnett, 2008). This then results in the theory of peace as freedom, which suggests that the means and ends of peace and development practices should be to ensure the equitable distribution of economic opportunities, political freedom, social opportunities, transparency guarantees, protective security and freedom from direct violence (Barnett, 2008).

The study suggests that peace is an essential factor in the development of a nation, which in turn results to a society's autonomy. Hence, the peace settlement in the Bangsamoro region is deemed significant in securing resilient peace as well as socio-political and economic growth. The outcome of peace governance projects between civil society organizations (CSOs), Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) and the Institute of Autonomy and Governance (IAG) will mirror the 'theory of peace as freedom' by presenting four out of six distinct freedoms enumerated in Galtung and

Sen's combined theory. The following have been achieved through the three projects highlighted in this study: political freedom, transparency guarantees, protective security and freedom from direct violence. A detailed description of how these four elements were achieved by the above-mentioned actors through their peace governance projects will further be elaborated in the presentation of data.

B. Conceptual Framework

In the area of peace and development in the Philippines, the KAS office works directly with its long-term institutional partner, the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG).

IAG plays an essential role as KAS' local partner because it enables the latter to work with various civil society organizations in Mindanao. The study looked at the partnership of KAS with IAG to enable the assessment of KAS' work with CSOs in its mutual effort towards peace and development in Mindanao. The capacity building activities implemented consists of civic and political education, dialogue forums, training of civil society leaders and study tours. Their joint cooperation illustrates that their work not only results in peace governance in Mindanao, but also serves as the Philippines' contribution to peace in the ASEAN.

Peace Governance in Mindanao and the Philippines' Contribution to the ASEAN

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

The following chapter encompasses the methodology applied by the researcher. It discusses the research designs and methods, the research locale, the research participants, the research gathering procedure the analysis of data.

A. Research Design and Methods

The study used a qualitative research design. It was a case study on peace governance in the Philippines, and how the role of a political foundation in ASEAN member countries, such as the Philippines, aids in achieving peace in their respective territories. The chosen foundation is the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) Philippines Office. Three projects/programs were highlighted in the study towards which KAS have different partnerships with. A face-to-face interview with the current KAS Philippines country director was conducted, while the questionnaire method for the previous KAS country director was followed. Moreover, a face-to-face interview with the program managers was accomplished. Also, face-to face interviews or the questionnaire method depending on the availability of the heads of the respective organizations were executed.

B. Research Locale

The study locale was set within Metro Manila. Though IAG, the main partner organization, is based in Cotabato, Mindanao, its executive director visits the KAS

Philippines' office at least once a month. For the previous KAS country director who is already back in Germany, the questionnaire was sent through e-mail. Additionally, for the program managers who were no longer with KAS, the questionnaire was sent to them per e-mail. Also, the executive directors of the two NGOs were interviewed via questionnaires sent to them via e-mail. Due to the ongoing pandemic when the research was conducted, all interviews except for the current KAS country director was carried out online.

C. Research Participants

The criteria of the research participant were based on their sufficient knowledge towards the projects that have been chosen for this research; and their capacity and position to respond to the interview questions. The research participants were as follows:

1. KAS Country Director 2015-2018

- His knowledge and involvement in the DEPAdev and DELACSE Phase 1 projects.

2. KAS Country Director 2018-2019

- His knowledge and involvement in the DELACSE Phase 1 and 2 projects.

3. IAG Executive Director

- His knowledge and involvement in the DEPAdev, DELACSE Phase 1 and 2 projects.

4. Program and Project Managers in charge for the respective projects

- Their knowledge and involvement in the DEPAdev and DELACSE Phase 1 and 2 projects.

5. Bangsamoro Women Service Center and Initiatives for International Dialogue and Pakigdait Executive Directors

- Their knowledge and involvement in the DEPAdev and DELACSE Phase 1 and 2 projects.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The research followed the timeframe below:

Month	Stage
January - April 2020	Interviews and Collection of Data
May 2020	Analysis of Data and Consultation with the Thesis Committee
May-July 2020	Thesis Write-up
August 2020	Editing of the Thesis
30 September 2020	Submission of the Thesis

The step-by-step procedures for the data gathering were as follows:

Step 1: The researcher set appointments with the respective interviewees.

Step 2: The researcher conducted a face-to-face interview and sent a questionnaire to the interviewee depending on their availability.

Step 3: The researcher executed a face-to-face interview with the present KAS country director. Meanwhile a questionnaire was sent to the former KAS country director from 2015-2018.

Step 4: The researcher yielded the data with regards to the KAS projects from the KAS database.

Step 5: The gathered data was analyzed. The said data was descriptively recorded and submitted to the thesis committee for approval.

Step 6: The researcher commenced with the thesis write-up.

Step 7: The write-up was submitted to the thesis committee for suggestions and approval.

The response to the interviews conducted and questionnaires submitted were validated by the respective annual project activity reports submitted to KAS Philippines' office and KAS Head Office in Berlin for auditing. The researcher had access to said files while she was still Program Manager at the KAS Philippines office when the study was being conducted.

E. Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the data in the following manner. First, the gathered data was transcribed and was then organized accordingly to the objectives and questions.

Second, the culled data was coded according to their concepts, properties, and patterns, i.e. depending on the theories used for the research.

Third, the data was then validated. by the respective annual project activity reports submitted to KAS Philippines' office and KAS Head Office in Berlin for auditing.

Lastly, the conclusion of the data was made through the analysis of stating the findings and research outcomes based on the research objectives.

Chapter V.

DATA PRESENTATION

The following chapter intends to present KAS' history and its nature, KAS' Philippines history and initiatives, KAS' partnership with IAG, and cooperation projects between KAS, IAG and CSOs namely, the Democratic Party Development Bangsamoro (DEPAdev) and the Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) Phases 1 and 2.

A. KAS History and Nature of Organization.

It was on 20 December 1955 that the "Society for Christian Democratic Civic Education" which later became the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) was founded. When what is now known as the KAS held its first educational seminar in Eichholz, Germany in December 1956, nobody even thought of the possibility of working internationally yet. The Society for Christian Democratic Civic Education mainly aimed at giving young people from Germany a sound civic education. In 1958, the Society changed its name to "Eichholz Political Academy". The courses offered over the following months pursued similar themes, ranging from German policies after the end of the Second World War, to the concept of the Social Market Economy, to how to organize and set up a political party.

Very soon, the founders of what is now the KAS's European and International Cooperation Department did not want to limit themselves to offering civic education within Germany. The idea was to support the educational work of Christian Democrats

all over the world. And when in 1960 the first major debates on development assistance in the German Bundestag started, it was only a matter of time before the first resident representatives were posted to open offices of the KAS abroad. The first countries to see foreign offices of the KAS were Venezuela in April, and Chile in November of 1963.

The early years of the KAS's International Cooperation department saw a focus on Latin American countries. A reason for that was the fact that it was more difficult to find suitable partners in Africa, the Middle East, and Asia. This was partly due to ties with former colonial powers, particularly in the Middle East and Asia due to the lack of institutions that were based on Christian values.

In 1964, the Academy changed its name to 'Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung für politische Bildung und Studienförderung e. V.' (Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung for Civic Education and Scholarships). In the very same year, the KAS set foot in Africa (Cameroon and Tanzania) and in the Philippines, as the very first country in Asia, with the support of Christian trade unions in the country.

From 1967 onwards, humanitarian aid was provided in South Vietnam. A first project was launched in Indonesia in 1968, and the first resident representatives also began their work in India, Sri Lanka, and South Korea. By 1970, the KAS was represented in 14 countries in the Caribbean and Latin America, in six countries in Africa, and in six countries in Asia, with a total of 60 resident representatives.

In 1976, 'Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung' received its final name, which was to become the hallmark for civic education in Germany and political development cooperation all around the globe. The initial successes led to a period of development and expansion between 1974 and 1989.

The KAS's work worldwide is based on the principles of freedom, justice, and solidarity. The Foundation aspires to make a contribution to the promotion of democracy, the rule of law, and a social market economy. To foster peace and freedom, it encourages a continuous dialog at the national and international levels, as well as the exchange between cultures and religions.

The KAS is a political foundation, closely associated with the Christian Democratic Union of Germany (CDU). As co-founder of the CDU, and the first Chancellor of the Federal Republic of Germany, Konrad Adenauer (1876- 1967) united Christian-social, conservative and liberal traditions. His name is synonymous with the democratic reconstruction of Germany, the firm alignment of foreign policy with the trans-Atlantic community of values, the vision of a unified Europe, and an orientation towards the social market economy. His intellectual heritage continues to serve both as the KAS's aim, as well as its obligation today.

The KAS's European and international cooperation efforts strive to enable people to live self-determined lives in freedom and dignity. Structurally, the department is based on two kinds of programs: 1) the country programs, and 2) the regional sector programs. The country programs are based on fixed partner programs and flexible measures which are chosen by the delegated representative of the KAS in the

respective country due to an analysis of demand and cooperation with the partner organizations. With its regional sector programs, the KAS promotes a long-term embodiment of structures that are based on the rule of law, as well as a free and independent media in the project countries.

In the rising political and economic world powers, China and India, the further development of the rule of law, good governance, and poverty reduction are in the focus of the Foundation's activities. Moreover, both countries are becoming dialogue partners in questions on the future world economic order and global security. In Central and Southeast Asia, the KAS provides programs on the establishment and consolidation of democracy and the civil society, conflict prevention, and interreligious dialogue.

Currently, the KAS in Germany operates from two conference centers and 16 regional offices across the country— with its headquarters being in Sankt Augustin and Berlin. Within Germany alone, it employs almost 500 staff in seven departments. Today, the Foundation hosts more than 200 projects in around 100 countries on four continents, with about 80 field offices with more than 400 local staff outside of Germany.

B. KAS Philippines History and Initiatives.

The Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung opened its first office in the Asian continent in the Philippines. Being a country in which the vast majority of the population ascribe themselves to the Christian faith and where Christian trade unions were already in

place and active, it seemed only natural that the Philippines would become the KAS's first hosting country in Asia.

The Foundation's early activities in the Philippines were focused on the support of trade unions, rural development, community development, and youth work. Furthermore, right from the start, the KAS Philippines supported the Christian/Muslim democratic movements under Raul S. Manglapus. However, there was a significant setback for the Foundation's activities in the country when President Ferdinand Marcos declared martial law in the Philippines (1972-1981).

Asia has undergone enormous changes over the last 50 years, hence, the activities of the KAS in the region have changed accordingly. Turning points for the KAS's involvement in the region were the democracy movements in the region, as well as the collapse of the Eastern Bloc. Democratization processes in Asia regained strength after 1986 with the removal of the Philippine dictator Ferdinand Marcos through the people's power revolution (EDSA revolution).

The German government under Chancellor Helmut Kohl was the first European government to develop an Asia strategy that took account of the momentous changes that had taken place. Significantly, the government's understanding of the role of Asia had changed, also the perception within the KAS shifted at the time. Thereafter, an entirely new concept for Asia was developed and the International Department of KAS was created.

The KAS' work from then on focused on issues such as reforms of parliament, committees, political parties, and non-governmental organizations. The topic of setting up constitutional structures, as well as foreign and security policy, thus became increasingly prominent in the KAS's Asia work.

In the Philippines, ever since the late 1980's, the main activities of the KAS have focused on Social Market Economy, Institutional and Political Reform, and Peace and Development in Mindanao.

The KAS Philippines aims to develop programs that help strengthen the democratic institutions and procedures in the country. Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung cooperates with governmental institutions, political parties, the academe, civil society organizations and handpicked elites, building strong partnerships along the way. Together with their partners they make a contribution to the creation of an international order that enables every country to develop in freedom and under its own responsibility. Human beings in their distinctive dignity, and with their rights and responsibilities, are at the heart of the KAS's work guided by the conviction that human beings are the starting point in the effort to bring about social justice and democratic freedom, while promoting sustainable economic activity. By bringing people together who embrace their responsibilities in society, active networks in the political and economic spheres, as well as in society itself, are developed. The KAS provides guidance on the basis of political know-how and knowledge, thus contributing to shaping the globalization process along more socially equitable, ecologically sustainable, and economically efficient lines.

C. The Partnership Between KAS and IAG

The Institute for Autonomy and Governance, based in Cotabato City in the west of the island of Mindanao, was established in 2001 because of want and necessity. The early 2000 was a period of instability and uncertainty for Mindanao. Back then, the implementation of the 1996 peace agreement of the Philippine government with the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF) was precarious under the administration of President Joseph Estrada who launched in 2000 an all-out war against the other Moro revolutionary group, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF). The Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) which was envisioned as the political structure for Moro self-governance in line with the 1996 Peace Agreement was ineffective and its leadership was generally perceived as lacking in capacities, corrupt and driven by their own political and economic interests. The failures of the ARMM to promote peace and economic development fueled people's disbelief of autonomy as a solution to the Moro rebellion. Instead of forcing submission of the Moro people to government's brand of autonomy, Estrada's all-out war further radicalized the revolutionary fronts to revert to its historical demand for independence. It is in this context of deadlock, uncertainty and hopelessness in Mindanao's future that the Institute for Autonomy and Governance was born. Started as a program under the College of Law of Notre Dame University under Law Dean Benedicto Bacani and inspired by University President Fr. Eliseo Mercado, Jr., OMI, IAG developed into an independent institute devoted to research, training and technical assistance to evolve genuine autonomy and good governance as a way to peace and development in the southern Philippines. An institutional partnership agreement with the KAS Philippines was then forged in 2004,

which enabled IAG to sustainably implement its core programs. To date, this institutional partnership with the KAS remains strong and robust.

IAG'S programs are guided by these frameworks in its partnership with KAS:

a. *Promoting autonomy and good governance as a means for sustainable peace and development in Mindanao.* This is the primary mandate of IAG. In partnership with the KAS, IAG is taking the lead in training, advocacy and research for meaningful decentralization of powers and administration to regional and local government units in the ARMM. This is the rationale for programs to capacitate Local Government units in the ARMM and the Iranun Development Council, an area in one of its provinces. In promoting meaningful autonomy and good governance in local levels and local communities, IAG provides the platform towards productive relations between local government units (LGUs) and the regional autonomous government especially in the light of the establishment of the new political entity for the Bangsamoro. In cooperation with the KAS, IAG is providing technical assistance in crafting the Bangsamoro Basic Law particularly in the areas of political autonomy and structures of government, political parties and elections. The KAS together with IAG conducted a series of seminars on the ministerial system, political party and electoral systems for the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) and the Bangsamoro Transition Commission (BTC), which is crafting the Basic Law for the new Bangsamoro political entity. The former KAS Philippines' Director Dr. Peter Köppinger has on numerous occasions lend his expertise on parliamentary, electoral political party and decentralized governmental systems in the crafting of the Basic Law.

b. Inclusive and holistic peace process that culminates in policies and structures that will promote social cohesion as key to peace and development.

IAG provides the platform where stakeholders can discuss, dialogue and debate on the substance and form of the structures for meaningful Bangsamoro self-governance. Together with the KAS, the European Union (EU) and Development Consultants (DEVCON), IAG implements the three-year, EU co-funded project IPDEV, to promote the rights and welfare of the indigenous peoples in the ARMM.

c. Security Reform, normalization and policing in the area of autonomy.

In partnership with the KAS, IAG has been involved in crafting policies and capacity building for the security sector in the region. It has developed modules on the role and contribution of the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP) and the Philippine National Police (PNP) in Mindanao peace building. The Framework Agreement on the Bangsamoro (FAB) and the new basic law shape the structures and policies on how to bring and maintain peace and security in the communities. The roles of the security sector such as the military and the police in the new political entity are subject of discussions and debate. IAG contributes to open and robust discussions in the local and national level on the best ways to structure policing in the proposed new political entity.

Civil society plays a crucial role in the functioning of a democratic society, often operating as a watchdog to keep governments to account and to advocate for the interests of different sectors of society. For civil society leaders to be able to carry out their role effectively and efficiently, to give policy input and work together with local administrations, it is vital that a good understanding of democratic decision-making

processes exists and that mechanisms are becoming established to cooperate with democratically elected politicians on moving the Bangsamoro region forward either as an autonomous region or a federal state.

D. Cooperation Projects between KAS, IAG and other CSOs

The three cooperation projects between KAS, IAG and other CSOs, namely the Democratic Party Development Bangsamoro (DEPAdev) and the Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) Phases 1 and 2 have significantly contributed to peace development in the Bangsamoro region by enhancing the role of civil society organizations through its various capacity building activities. These projects have provided an array of training to prepare decision-makers and civil society leaders for active engagement in the new political framework in the new Bangsamoro political entity by enhancing leadership abilities. All three projects promote active civil society participation as a means to good governance and sustainable peace in the region.

Democratic Party Development Bangsamoro (DEPAdev)

Overall objective.

The overall objective of the DEPAdev was the contribution to a peaceful transition in the establishment and democratic functioning of the new autonomous political entity, known as the Bangsamoro, in Muslim Mindanao. The project was implemented from 01 September 2015 to 28 February 2017.

After decades of struggle between Muslim liberation movements and the Government of the Philippines, the Comprehensive Agreement on the Bangsamoro (CAB) signed in March 2014 was the most promising chance for peace. After the draft of the Bangsamoro Basic Law was handed over to parliament, all stakeholders expected the passage by the House of Representatives and Senate in 2015. Nonetheless, during the time that the DEPAdev was implemented, the overall situation remained fragile. If the attempts for a smooth transition from ARMM to the new autonomous Bangsamoro entity failed, peace could not be guaranteed in Muslim Mindanao. Therefore, it was of crucial significance to contribute in the peaceful transition to the establishment and democratic functioning of the new autonomous Bangsamoro in Muslim Mindanao. The DEPAdev addressed obstacles which could otherwise have negative effects on this development in order to work on sustainable peace within the region.

Specific objective.

The specific objectives of the project were: (1) to train and educate Muslim, Christian, and Indigenous groups in order to enable them for active political participation under a parliamentary system; and (2) to empower stakeholders to transform their groups and operate them as functional genuine programmatic political parties based on the rule of law.

Both specific objectives built a foundation on which active civil society participation within the autonomous region was possible. The project believed that

democratic well-trained and politically educated stakeholders are the backbone of a functioning political system in the Bangsamoro. The project also considered that the vehicle for stakeholders to cater the needs of the population was to have genuine democratic political parties. By being organized as registered political parties, the supporters, members, and leaders of those parties can integrate their programs into political processes.

Intended Results.

The project intended to achieve the following results:

Result 1: To establish genuine political parties operating in the Bangsamoro. The formation of genuine political parties is essential for citizens to aggregate and articulate their interests in the political sphere. The establishment of such parties will be supported by training and seminars guiding the stakeholders of interested groups towards technical and programmatic skills which enable them to formally found, register and operate parties.

Result 2: To enable civil society groups to gain a sound understanding of active political participation under the political system of the Bangsamoro. Since the entire political system of the future Bangsamoro will be new to the population, knowledge and education will be provided through the project. In understanding the nature and processes of the Bangsamoro political system, civil society groups will gain a sound understanding through which methods active political participation will be possible.

Result 3: To allow political parties and their respective groups in parliament in gaining advanced knowledge on parliamentary procedures

In order to operate efficiently and successfully within the constitutional framework laid out by the Bangsamoro Basic Law, it is necessary for political parties to gain advanced knowledge on the parliamentary system of the Bangsamoro. Since the presidential political system of the Philippines is distinctly different from the parliamentary system of the Bangsamoro, it is also important for the parliamentary groups of the parties, i.e. its elected members in the legislative body, to perform successfully as a group.

Role of KAS and IAG.

KAS, as contractual partner of the EU, has a background of huge project experience (worldwide about 200 ongoing projects with an annual turnover of over 90 million Euros, managed through KAS offices in about 80 countries; among them more than 20 ongoing projects co-funded by the EU; in the Philippines, projects and cooperation with local partners since 1968, several ongoing projects with an annual turnover of more than one Million Euro. KAS has close relations to national authorities (Executive, Legislative, and Judiciary). In this project, KAS was responsible for the following:

- communication and reporting to the European Commission;
- coordination of communication between the partner and of external visibility activities;

- identification, contracting, and implementation of the missions of short-term experts, including evaluations by an external evaluator;
- submission of narrative and financial reports (interim and final) to the European Commission;
- financial management, cash flow, accounting, and budget control;
- activity management, overseeing, quality control, and ensuring the timetable and deliverables;
- preparing documents for the final evaluation; and
- relations with national authorities.

IAG has consistently implemented programs to advance sustainable peace and development in Mindanao, founded on meaningful autonomy and good governance.

IAG was responsible for the following:

- communication with the target groups and the stakeholders involved in the action;
- implementation of basic orientation seminars and coordination of training, training of trainers, and consulting seminars with Muslim, Christian, and IP leaders and leaders of nonreligious/ non-ethnic organizations from Mindanao;
- support, coordination, and cooperation in the implementation of training and consulting activities;
- involvement in the implementation of dissemination activities;
- support of the advocacy activities on national legal and political framework in the action; and
- coordination with KAS with regards to project results meant for the final conference and publications.

**Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in
Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) – Phase 1**

Overall objective.

To contribute to democratic processes and peace in the Bangsamoro political entity (either Federal State or Autonomous Region). Since the proposed Bangsamoro Law has been shelved and was not yet clear when the promised Bangsamoro Autonomous Region or a new Federal Region will come into place, the new government of the Philippines seems committed to the Peace Process. The project was implemented from 1 March 2017 to 31 March 2018.

To ensure that the transition, when it happens, will be peaceful and constructive, it is essential to work with both political decision-makers and democratic forces in civil society at this point in time, so that trained and informed leaders are in place to manage the transition in a peaceful and democratic way, and help prevent a crisis from erupting in the Bangsamoro political entity.

Both target groups, decision-makers, and civil society leaders in the Bangsamoro political entity, are expected to hit the ground running once the new political framework in the region becomes a reality. To ensure a smooth transition from the current system, politicians and civil society representatives need to be better prepared than they are currently, and need exposure to federal systems outside the Philippines to learn from and be inspired by.

Specific Objective.

To prepare decision-makers and civil society leaders for active engagement in the new political framework in the new Bangsamoro political entity by enhancing leadership abilities.

Intended Results.

Result 1: Trained politicians and civil society leaders are able to assess, plan, adapt, and update the policies and mechanisms needed for a federal (or Autonomous) Bangsamoro region, considering any transitions from the newly-established Philippine government.

Result 2: Members of the target group are capacitated to formulate and articulate comprehensive policy inputs vis-à-vis the Bangsamoro Transition Commission and actors that shape current reform efforts.

Currently, there is a lack of political knowledge within the political elite and civil society leaders in the region on how best to achieve a smooth transition from the current Autonomous Region of Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) to a new framework of a Federal or Autonomous Bangsamoro region.

Capacity building and knowledge transfer on how to operate in a federal system, how to develop policies, introduce strategy papers and use political mechanisms is urgently needed to ensure that all relevant stakeholders are prepared

and have the knowledge to contribute to a smooth transition from the current system to a new one.

On a more detailed level, the project's activities will also enable politicians and civil society leaders to provide specific policy input to the Bangsamoro Transition Commission to ensure that the views of different stakeholders are included at the early planning stages.

Cooperation with other Projects.

The project aims to create synergies with other projects that KAS is carrying out in the Philippines, in particular, with work done by organisations that are part of the current DEPAdev project in Muslim Mindanao. These include: ARMM Regional Commission on Bangsamoro Women, Teduray Lambangian Women's Organization (TLWO Inc.), Organization of Teduray and Lambangian Conference (OTLAC), Consortium of Bangsamoro Civil Society (CBCS), Civil Society Organization Forum for Peace (CSOFP), Mindanao Commission on Women-Lanao, Chamber of Commerce and Industry Iligan Inc. (CCIFII) and Mindanao Peoples Peace Movement (MPPM).

Roles of KAS and IAG.

In this project, KAS has been responsible for:

- communication and reporting to the European Commission;
- coordination of communication between the partner and of external visibility activities;

- identification, contracting, and implementation of the missions of short-term experts, including evaluations by an external evaluator;
- financial management, cash flow, accounting, and budget control;
- activity management, overseeing, quality control, and ensuring the timetable and deliverables;
- preparing documents for the final evaluation; and
- relations with national authorities.

Meanwhile, IAG has been responsible for the:

- communication with the target groups and the stakeholders involved in the action;
- implementation of basic and advanced leadership seminars and coordination the training of trainers;
- support, coordination, and cooperation in the implementation of training and consulting activities;
- involvement in the implementation of dissemination activities;
- support of the lecture activities and the publication activities.

Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) – Phase 2

Overall objective.

This project was built on the concluded project Democratic Leadership and Civil Society Empowerment (DELACSE Bangsamoro – Phase 1). The proposed project

aims to up-scale the activities and programs that had been started under these two projects, particularly those that will contribute to the peaceful transition and democratic functioning of the new autonomous Bangsamoro political entity. To be specific, this project envisions to promote equal participation, peaceful dialogues, and political pluralism for good governance and sustainable peace in the region.

This continuity project stemmed from the strong demand of civil society organizations and political groups for sustained political and civic education in Bangsamoro. This is to instill critical thinking and develop the skills of civil society for them to adeptly participate in democratic processes. They realized that the Bangsamoro constituency needs to be informed on the unfolding political changes in the region so that they can objectively make informed decisions on every issue and challenges confronting them. To achieve this goal, the project will continue to work with CSOs and political groups who are actively involved in peacebuilding and political reforms by developing leadership capacity so that they can effectively direct their respective organizations, their immediate constituencies, and the general public to work for peace and democratic governance. Furthermore, the project will emphasize the participation of marginalized segments of society like women, youth, and indigenous peoples to make sure that these groups and sectors are not left out, in terms of participation, representation, and inclusion of their agenda in the process of building the Bangsamoro community and the future government.

Specific Objective.

Female and male political and civil society leaders actively participate in shaping, assessing, planning, adapting, and updating the policies and mechanisms needed for a Federal (or Autonomous) Bangsamoro region.

Result 1: CSO and political leaders have a better understanding of the evolving political landscape in Bangsamoro, and are equipped to engage in democratic and gender inclusive processes as political movements, parties, or advocacy groups.

Result 2: CSO and political groups actively engage all segments of the public to generate and develop policy inputs for policy dialogues and gender sensitive advocacy initiatives.

Result 3: Strengthened CSOs and CSO networks for a wide-ranging programs and sustained gender sensitive advocacy engagement.

Roles of KAS and IAG

In this project, IAG as the lead applicant has directly communicated and reported the progress and potential problems of the project to the FPI Regional Team in the EU Delegation in Bangkok. It has been responsible in doing coordination work with partner stakeholders and ensured proper and effective management of the project deliverables taking into account timely implementation of all activities based on the set timetable as well as making sure that the activities are relevant to the intended

outcome and outputs of the project. It has also directly managed the project funding, thereby strictly observing proper accounting systems, processes and procedures based on EU financial and accounting rules and procedures. It has maintained good working relations with local and national authorities by informing them about the project, especially its possible contribution to improving governance in Bangsamoro.

Meanwhile, KAS has been responsible for supporting IAG in all financial aspects relevant to the project. As the security situation in Mindanao is not always stable, IAG has transferred all project-related documents to KAS Manila for double checking and for filing, and also the project audit took place at the KAS premises in Manila. KAS has prepared the financial guidelines for the project binding to all partners and also supports the preparation of the financial report. In addition, KAS has been involved in the implementation of the study trip, as well as in the training for political party and civil society leaders. The financial support to third parties was also supported by KAS.

Role of Initiatives for International Dialogue (IID)

IID has complemented the IAG-KAS engagement by consolidating grassroots communities and organizations. IID has engaged them with local and national-level political leaders and institutions with major roles in the transitioning Bangsamoro. It directly reported to IAG the implementation of its activities and fund management in accordance with the general guidelines of the EU and of IAG and KAS. IID has participated in the inception workshop and coordination meetings to ensure the smooth flow of administrative, financial, and program implementation of the project

E. KAS Philippines contribution to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN

KAS' most noteworthy impact to peacebuilding is the empowerment of local actors and civil society organizations through a variety of capacity building activities. KAS has consistently designed a learning hub to capacitate CSO leaders especially in the Bangsamoro. This goal has been made possible through the implementation of its three projects, namely the DEPAdev, the DELACSE Phase 1 and the DELACSE Phase 2.

First, the DEPAdev built the foundation for both basic and intermediate political knowledge and civic education. In return, this enabled local stakeholders to actively participate in democratic peaceful political processes. The central aim of this project was to empower civil society in the conflict-ridden regions of Southern Philippines to actively participate in political decision processes which are at the basis of political pluralism. In this project, KAS together with IAG conducted seminars, workshops and training for selected groups; in particular underrepresented groups such as the indigenous peoples, women and youth organizations, and key MORO groups. Also, KAS and IAG were able to aid local actors in the formation and the registration of new civil society organizations and political parties. This certainly led to a sense of empowerment and enhanced degree of institutionalization among the democratic stakeholders in the region because they were given the opportunity to actively participate as a co-host in all the activities and not merely recipients of financial assistance from KAS. In addition, KAS was able to implement the DEPADdev in a

much more comprehensive dimension, since this was the first project to be co-funded by the European Union.

Second, the DELACSE Phase 1 is considered a continuation of the DEPADev. The project's goals satisfactorily sustained the awareness and capabilities of local political parties and civil society organizations. It helped them further achieve essential understanding and abilities in managing their respective organizations for the future implementation of the autonomous Bangsamoro political entity. The project activities resulted to accomplishing advanced level development objectives, particularly the contribution to a peaceful transition to the establishment and democratic functioning of the new political entity in Muslim Mindanao. The DELACSE project has left a significant impression for the future of the Bangsamoro because it is one of the very few "political" projects in the region. The overall consolidation of the CSOs brought about the dissemination and deeper understanding of political education.

Third, the DELACSE Phase 2 similarly conducted activities related to the first phase of the project. It has focused on the further development of capacities of political groups and civil society organizations in order for them to become more active participants in shaping the policies and democratic institutions in the newly established Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). With the implementation of the DELACSE Phase 2, it is believed that a more stable and peaceful society has been the result of good policies and the establishment of firm democratic institutions.

All in all, KAS has offered a learning hub to capacitate CSO leaders, especially in the Bangsamoro region. The entry of KAS through its development partner, the IAG, have greatly helped in building the foundational structures of peace. These institutions have effectively penetrated risky territories where government people do not dare go. A peaceful Mindanao spells a peaceful Philippines that bodes well for ASEAN regional stability and security. And a peaceful Philippines.

F. The challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN; and to the role of CSOs and non-ASEAN foundations

A number of challenges towards peacebuilding in Mindanao and the ASEAN as a whole have been gathered in this research. The view of the following entities and individuals have been divided below into that of KAS, KAS' projects, IAG, and the CSOs.

KAS

KAS believes that the challenges to peacebuilding root back to the complex historical conflicts of Muslim Mindanao. The intricate struggles have been an obstacle to peacebuilding itself. There are two major challenges that are deemed significant: (1) the lack of reliability and continuity of support from the national government because it has been impossible for relevant actors to predict which phase a new president would stand for; and (2) governance problems and dysfunctional political institutions: Corruption, governance deficits and clan-/dynasty-dominated politics are massive obstacles to any kind.

DEPAdev

One of the major challenges for the DEPAdev was working together with the immediate target groups of the project inclusive of the former rebel organizations which started transforming into political democratic movements. An example for one of the challenges encountered by other non-ASEAN foundations was the program of the Swiss non-governmental organization Fondation Suisse de Déminage (FSD). It includes building the capacity of transitory and established Bangsamoro authorities, including the establishment of a Bangsmaoro Mine Action Centre (BMAC), to coordinate and carry out mine action activities, and weapons and ammunition management. These types of challenges are still present in Muslim Mindanao.

DELACSE Phase 1

The challenges encountered during the first phase of this project were: (1) political instability such as threats from rebel groups; (2) absence of real political parties that will determine democratically the next set of leaders who will run in the next presidential elections; (3) the presence of political dynasties with some families that demerit democratic process in electing leaders who will run in the elections; and (4) political patronage, which is rooted in all levels of government in the Philippines.

For the DELACSE Phase 1, it was a challenge to not have a locally known and trustworthy local partner to implement the activities of the project. Therefore, the partnership with IAG made it possible to reach out to the CSOs.

DELACSE Phase 2

One of the big challenges to peacebuilding in the Philippines is the domination of elites over the poor segments of society. This social divide is manifested in both the political and economic life of Philippine society. The situation in Mindanao and in the newly created BARMM is reflective of this, whereby the political elites and so-called warlords and big clans are in control of the political institutions including big businesses and vast economic resources. Because of this, there is a seeming disconnection between the political leaders and those in the bureaucracy with civil society. On the other hand, the civil society for the longest time has lost the desire to contribute something for the country, thinking that at the end of the day, everything will end up into the hands of the few individuals or groups in power.

In addition, one of the challenges, though not a major one for KAS Philippines, is to address the inclination of some ASEAN countries for regionalism or tendencies to build strong alliances with countries within the region or to align with strong ASIAN countries like China. If ever this will happen, some SEA nations might say that they will not work with international organizations like KAS because it is a German foundation, therefore it might promote the European style of politics.

IAG

The pervasive clan culture and elite-driven politics still pose a risk to newfound stability in Mindanao following the recent political settlement with a major Moro revolutionary group. Many communities across the ASEAN region face the same

challenges. Being part of a reliable network of CSOs across ASEAN that values knowledge and skills exchange to this day remains a challenge for IAG.

CSOs

The intricate conflict in Mindanao is embedded in both historical and socio-political-structural context. It is complex in three contemporary types of conflicts namely; ideological, identity and resource-based. Conflicts in Mindanao reverberates the entire country and ASEAN. With these as a backdrop peacebuilding works are protracted and need cooperation of ASEAN nations but grounded in the local context.

For Pakigdait, as an interfaith grassroots peacebuilding CSO for almost two decades, they have experienced a limitation to elevate its advocacy inside formal institutions like the ASEAN. Indeed, Pakigdait is an active member of two international CSO platforms namely South East Asian Network of Civil Society Organisations (SEAN-CSO), a network of organizations from Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, Indonesia and Australia, and the United Religion Initiatives (URI), a global grassroots interfaith network that cultivates peace and justice by engaging people to bridge religious and cultural differences. Nonetheless, bringing forward these issues and advocacies in formal institutions as such is deemed insufficient.

Another challenge is the generational poverty and absence of educational opportunities that have remained the visible challenges, which are hard to address by the national government in peacemaking. The government should establish a sustained policy agenda for these two issues because poverty-stricken people are but

victims of a colonial society. This challenge is identical in several ASEAN countries. One cannot create peace for an entire population if more than half of them, or more, are economically impoverished and uneducated.

Lastly, the overlay of addressing the pandemic amid the skewed normalization track and political transition is foremost, coupled with festering and bursts of new armed conflict within the BARMM among and between Moro groups, fronts and clans, IPs and Moros, government and other armed elements. In ASEAN, the pandemic has also exacerbated persisting conflicts and displacements especially as governments have resorted to draconian measures in addressing the health crisis.

G. The problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN

The implementation of KAS peacebuilding activities in Mindanao has been feasible due to the partnership with IAG, to which the latter provided connections with local CSOs and other stakeholders in the region. Alongside their efforts, KAS was faced with several challenges, to which the most prominent were elite-driven processes, political inequality, political clans, and warlordism. These were some of the list of issues encountered by KAS during the execution of their peacebuilding efforts through the DEPAdev, DELACSE Phase 1, and DELACSE Phase 2.

First, the environmental setting for the DEPAdev was challenging per se. Hence, the discussion of the basic principles of working on the political transition of the Bangsamoro region was essential. Since the funding for the project was sufficient,

it was possible to carry out as many workshops and trainings as possible for the Bangsamoro parties and political movements. However, after the project duration, the CSOs were challenged to apply the basic principles in their respective organizational structures without the help of KAS.

Second, the DELACSE Phase 1 stumbled upon numerous problems during the implementation of the project, such as the Marawi siege which lasted for almost 5 months. The CSOs from Lanao del Norte were not able to partake in the project's activities due to the on-going war and political instability in the province. In addition, the on-going progression of developing the then Autonomous Region for Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) to a new Bangsamoro Autonomous Region was prevalent during the time the DELACSE Phase 1 was implemented. Nonetheless, this was not seen as a problem by KAS, but rather an opportunity to work hand in hand with the decision-makers, stakeholders, and key persons to introduce the concepts of the new Bangsamoro government.

Third, the DELACSE Phase 2 generally encountered an evident limitation to work at grassroots level due to the peace and security challenges in Mindanao.

All in all, KAS faced challenges along their peacebuilding efforts. It was challenging enough to gain trust from local actors, especially with KAS being a foreign organization. However, it has mostly been an advantage for KAS to be neutral and independent from the national government or any other government in Asia. KAS was able to establish its identity as an "honest broker". Through KAS' policy to constantly work together with local actors and experts, rather than serving as a mere donor, one

could conclude that KAS has no serious disadvantages compared to other local or regional foundations.

H. KAS Philippines and its partner CSOs recommendations to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts

The KAS country director from 2015 to 2018 recommends to seek the help and support of outcome-driven regional and international democratic actors, both from within and outside the Asian region. He stated that “the processes that lead to lasting peace are mostly the ones that are based on best practices in peacebuilding. However, it is crucial to always modify the selected best practice approaches and adapt them to local/regional conditions.”

The KAS Country director from 2018 to 2021 mentions that “the significance of having local stakeholders as partners who have a cultural and linguistic background, which is part of the acceptance is essential to peace building efforts.”

IAG’s Executive Director believes that capacity building for peace is not only about changing and improving structures and processes, but also building mindsets that promote culture of inclusivity and efficiency in governance. Also, he states that “the ownership of these structures and processes must be built, not only by those in government, but especially by the constituents.” It is necessary to balance interests of different groups and paradigms where planning, design and implementation of

policies, i.e. where structures and policies involve rebel leaders, technocrats, and other political actors.

DEPAdev's Project Manager sees the need for an empowered civil society as a foundation for peace and participatory democracy, the DEPAdev project aimed at promoting genuine political parties and movements within the future autonomous region Bangsamoro. He mentions that "access to political decision-making for civil society actors representing different social groups is the key component. This also applies to the current political situation in other ASEAN member states, such as Myanmar or Cambodia."

The DELACSE 1 Project Manager states that "change in the system should not only happen in the Bangsamoro. Although it can be considered as a good example to all provinces in the countries that desire to become autonomous regions, there should be a joint effort from the national government to continue its quest in pushing for a federal-parliamentary form of government. It will be an incredible challenge for the Duterte administration to fulfill its promise to pursue this gigantic shift from a unitary-presidential government to federal. However, this is seen as a major solution to keep this country at peace. Otherwise, one cannot really thrive as a nation if one remains to be disgruntled under a centralized government whose economy only concentrates in the key cities and development only trickles down to the few underprivileged areas." Hence, Faderan also recommended to KAS and IAG to institutionalize the database of the local CSO partners, as this is the key to establish more engagements and to build a wider array of networks both locally and internationally.

The DELACSE 2 Project Manager proposes “ASEAN member states to continue its investment in democratization initiatives primarily to emphasize the need for citizen’s participation in governance, maintain strong check and balance in government, and build strong democratic political institutions to ensure that no single individual or groups will dominate the political life of a country.”

The Pakigdait Incorporated Executive Director submits that local context is essential in formulating peacebuilding efforts. Proper usage of conflict analysis tools and correct appreciation of the local context of conflict then would help a lot for a sound peacebuilding effort. One should not be afraid to revise the process if it is necessary. People on the ground know best, they just do not know the technical terms or jargon by so called experts in peace and conflict. Thus, this needs patience in listening to them with a purpose and respect. She further states that “the ASEAN member states need to bind stronger cooperation against terrorism, and strengthen cross-border cooperation for peacebuilding efforts.”

The Bangsamoro Women Service Center Executive Director quotes that “before rainy days come you have to fortify yourself with shelter structure.” Therefore, she states that “before an untoward incident recurs, all the preventive measures towards structural violence must be put in place. In case there are still political snags in diplomatic relationships between countries, such must be ironed out, the earlier the better. The undying claim of the Tausug people in Southern Philippines for their sovereign and proprietary rights over Sabah remains a challenge to peacemaking

initiatives.” She believes that concerned ASEAN countries must act together for peace.

The Executive Director for the Initiatives for International Dialogue suggests that “the ASEAN can start involving civil society more in its mechanisms, such as the ASEAN Institute for Peace and Reconciliation (AIPR), better even if civil society has actual representations in the body.” They have a Governing Council that is composed of the government, therefore they can provide the slots of the Advisory Board to civil society, academe, or even the private sector or faith-based group.

Chapter VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This final chapter aims to present the research study's summary, conclusion and recommendation.

A. Summary

The core focus of the research was to discover how KAS Philippines has contributed to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN. In the area of peace and development in the Philippines, KAS worked directly with its long-term institutional partner, the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG).

IAG plays an essential role as KAS' local partner because it enabled the latter to work with various civil society organizations in Mindanao. The study looked at the partnership of KAS with IAG to enable the assessment of KAS' work with CSOs in its mutual effort towards peace and development in Mindanao. The capacity building activities implemented consists of civic and political education, dialogue forums, training of civil society leaders and study tours. Their joint cooperation illustrates that their work has not only resulted in peace governance in Mindanao, but has also served as the Philippines' contribution to peace in the ASEAN.

The study used a qualitative research design. It was a case study on peace governance in the Philippines, and how the role of a political foundation in ASEAN member countries, such as the Philippines, aids in achieving peace in their respective

territories. The chosen foundation is the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung (KAS) Philippines Office. Three projects/programs were highlighted in the study towards which KAS have different partnerships with. A face-to-face interview with the current KAS Philippines country director was conducted, while the questionnaire method for the previous KAS country director was followed. Initially, face-to face interviews or the questionnaire method depending on the availability of the heads of the respective organizations were scheduled. However, due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 and the implementation of the nationwide lockdown, the researcher was not able to proceed as planned and only three out of the ten civil society organizations responded to the questionnaires sent. Nonetheless, the gathered data is deemed sufficient to address the goals and objectives of the study.

B. Conclusion

The KAS Philippines early activities in the Philippines since its establishment in 1964 were focused on the support of trade unions, rural development, community development, and youth work. From the very beginning, the KAS Philippines supported the Christian/Muslim democratic movements. Since the late 1980's, the main activities of the KAS have focused on Social Market Economy, Institutional and Political Reform, and Peace and Development in Mindanao. The KAS Philippines aims to develop programs that help strengthen the democratic institutions and procedures in the country. The KAS cooperates with governmental institutions, political parties, the academe, civil society organizations and handpicked elites, building strong partnerships along the way. Together with their partners they make a contribution to the creation of an international order that enables every country to develop in freedom

and under its own responsibility. By bringing people together who embrace their responsibilities in society, active networks in the political and economic spheres, as well as in society itself, are developed. As a whole, the KAS provides guidance on the basis of political know-how and knowledge, thus contributing to shaping the globalization process along more socially equitable, ecologically sustainable, and economically efficient lines.

The three cooperation projects between KAS, IAG and other CSOs, namely the Democratic Party Development Bangsamoro (DEPAdev) and the Democratic Leadership and Active Civil Society Empowerment in Bangsamoro (DELACSE Bangsamoro) Phases 1 and 2 have significantly contributed to peace development in the Bangsamoro region by enhancing the role of civil society organizations through its various capacity building activities. These projects have provided an array of training to prepare decision-makers and civil society leaders for active engagement in the new political framework in the new Bangsamoro political entity by enhancing leadership abilities. All three projects promote active civil society participation as a means to good governance and sustainable peace in the region.

The research study commenced with the aim to place emphasis on the role of KAS Philippines and its contribution to peace governance in the ASEAN through their projects in Mindanao with various civil society organizations. The documentation of the various peacebuilding activities in sustaining peace and promoting development in conflict-affected areas can be seen as a guide in building a resilient, peaceful, and more stable ASEAN. The implementation of the various projects did not go without encountering any challenges for all concerned parties. For KAS, it was a major

challenge to gain trust from local actors, especially with KAS being a foreign organization. For IAG, being part of a reliable network of CSOs across ASEAN that values knowledge and skills exchange to this day remains to be a challenge. For CSOs, they are challenged by the generational poverty and absence of educational opportunities which are hard to address by the national government in peacemaking. In addition, the current pandemic has added up to the existing problems being encountered in the Bangsamoro region as well as in other ASEAN countries.

All in all, the current development in the Bangsamoro not only sets the groundwork of security, inclusivity, and improvement in the region, but it also brings more opportunities for the people of Mindanao, the Philippines, and the ASEAN Community. Moreover, the realization of the peace process contributes to ASEAN's increasing knowledge and best practices in the advancement of a culture of peace and respect for diversity among its peoples.

C. Recommendation

After a thorough analysis of data, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. This research study suggests that peace in the Philippines does not only benefit the country itself, but also towards the whole peace and welfare of the ASEAN Community as a whole. Therefore, it is vital to research into different forms of cooperation with external entities to be able to learn and apply diverse approaches to peace governance in the individual concerned ASEAN member states.

2. Since KAS is an external actor towards which the ASEAN could possibly derive potential post-conflict reconstruction and peacebuilding approaches from. It could share its best practices with other member states that experience the same conflict in their respective territories.

3. To expand the research on other KAS country offices in the ASEAN member states and be able to highlight the various cooperation partnerships they have with the civil society organizations in their area.

4. To conduct further research on other German foundations and their work with civil society organizations. The different German foundations have various approaches to implement their goals and objectives. Hence, it is a significant contribution to be able to use these approaches as a model for their best practices.

5. This study is considered helpful and informative for other civil society organizations in ASEAN member states because it would give them an idea on how to work with a foreign organization that could enable them to develop peace in their areas of concern.

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APPENDIX A

The interviews conducted were with the following individuals:

1. KAS Country Director 2015-2018, Online Interview
2. KAS Country Director 2018-2021, Face to Face Interview
3. IAG Executive Director, Online Interview
4. Project Manager for DEPAdev, Online Interview
5. Project Manager DELACSE 1, Online Interview
6. Project Manager DELCASE 2, Online Interview
7. Executive Director Pakigdait Incorporated Executive Director, Online Interview
8. Executive Director Bangsamoro Women Service Center, Online Interview
9. Executive Director Initiatives for International Dialogue, Online Interview

APPENDIX B

Interview Questionnaire **for the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung Philippines Country Director 2015-2018**

1. How long was your tour of duty as a country director in the Philippines? Kindly indicate the begin and the end.
2. How did KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DEPAdev project?
3. How did KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DELACSE phase 1 project?
4. How did KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its annual Kusog Mindanaw conference?
5. What were the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
6. What were the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN foundations like KAS Philippines?
7. What were the problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
8. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with your partner civil society organization in both DEPAdev and DELACSE projects?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
9. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.
 - a. When did the DEPAdev project commence and end?
 - b. When did the DELACSE phase 1 project commence and end?
 - c. How will you assess the DEPAdev project in terms of promoting peace?
 - d. How will you assess the DELACSE phase 1 project in terms of promoting peace?

10. What can you, as a former country director of KAS Philippines, recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX C

Interview Questionnaire for the Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung Philippines Country Director 2018-2021

1. How does KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DELACSE Phase 2 project?

2. How does KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its annual Kusog Mindanaw conference?

3. What are the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

4. What are the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN foundations, like KAS Philippines?

5. What are the problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

6. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with your partner civil society organization in the DELACSE Phase 2 project?

- Civic / Political Education
- Trainings
- Dialogue Forums
- Study Tours
- Others (Kindly specify):

7. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.

From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.

a. When did the DELACSE phase 2 project commence?

b. How will you assess the DELACSE phase 2 project in terms of promoting peace?

8. What can KAS Philippines recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX D

Interview Questionnaire for the DEPAdev Project Manager

1. How long was your tour of duty as the DEPAdev project manager for KAS Philippines? Kindly indicate the begin and the end.
2. How did KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DEPAdev project?
3. What were the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
4. What were the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN foundations like KAS Philippines?
5. What were the problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
6. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with your partner civil society organization in the DEPAdev project?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
7. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.
 - a. When did the DEPAdev project commence?
 - b. How will you assess the DEPAdev project in terms of promoting peace?
8. What can you, as a former project manager for KAS Philippines recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX E

Interview Questionnaire for the DELACSE Phase 1 Project Manager

1. How long was your tour of duty as the DELACSE phase 1 project manager for KAS Philippines? Kindly indicate the begin and the end.
2. How did KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DELACSE phase 1 project?
3. What were the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
4. What were the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN foundations like KAS Philippines?
5. What were the problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
6. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with your partner civil society organization in the DEPAdev project?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
7. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.
 - a. When did the DELACSE phase 1 project commence and end?
 - b. How will you assess the DELACSE phase 1 project in terms of promoting peace?
8. What can you, as a former project manager for KAS Philippines recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX F

Interview Questionnaire for the DELACSE Phase 2 Project Manager

1. How long is your tour of duty as the DELACSE phase 2 project manager for KAS Philippines? Kindly indicate the begin and the end.
2. How does KAS Philippines contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DELACSE phase 2 project?
3. What are the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
4. What are the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN foundations like KAS Philippines?
5. What are the problems encountered by KAS Philippines in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
6. Which among the following activities do you conduct together with your partner civil society organization in the DELACSE phase 2 project?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
7. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.
8. What can you, as a current project manager for KAS Philippines recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview

APPENDIX G

Interview Questionnaire **for the Institute of Autonomy and Governance (IAG)** **Executive Director**

1. How long have you been the executive director of IAG?
2. How long has IAG been an institutional partner with KAS Philippines?
3. How did IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through the DEPAdev project?
4. How did IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its DELACSE phase 1 project?
5. How does IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its on-going DELACSE phase 2 project?
6. How does IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN through its annual Kusog Mindanaw conference?
7. What were the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
8. What were the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN institutions like IAG?
9. What were the problems encountered by IAG in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
10. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with KAS Philippines in the DEPAdev and DELACSE phase 1 and 2 projects?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
11. From the above chosen activities, kindly describe the said activity.
 - a. When did the DEPAdev project commence and end?
 - b. When did the DELACSE phase 1 project commence and end?
 - c. When did the DELACSE phase 2 project commence and will end?
 - d. How will you assess the DEPAdev project in terms of promoting peace?

- e. How will you assess the DELACSE phase 1 project in terms of promoting peace?
- f. How will you assess the DELACSE phase 2 project in terms of promoting peace?
- 12. Which civil society organizations have participated in the DEPAdev project?
- 13. Which civil society organizations have participated in the DELACSE phase 1 project?
- 14. Which civil society organizations have participated in the DELACSE phase 2 project?
- 15. Which civil society organizations participate in the annual Kusog Mindanaw conference that also contribute to peace-building in the ASEAN?
- 16. What can IAG recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX H

Interview Questionnaire for the Mindanao Organization for the Pakigdait Incorporated Executive Director

1. How long have you been the executive director of the Pakigdait Incorporated?
2. How long has Pakigdait Incorporated been a part of KAS Philippines projects through the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)?
3. In your opinion, how did KAS Philippines through IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN?
4. What are the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
5. What are the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN institutions like Pakigdait Incorporated?
6. What were the problems encountered by Pakigdait Incorporated in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
7. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with KAS Philippines?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
8. In which KAS projects has Pakigdait Incorporated been a part of (DEPADEV, DELACSE Phase 1 or DELACSE Phase 2)?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX I

Interview Questionnaire **for the Bangsamoro Women Service Center (BWSC) Executive Director**

1. How long have you been the executive director of the Bangsamoro Women Service Center (BWSC)?

2. How long has BWSC been a part of KAS Philippines projects through the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)?

3. In your opinion, how did KAS Philippines through IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN?

4. What are the challenges to peace building in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

5. What are the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN institutions like BWSC?

6. What were the problems encountered by BWSC in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?

7. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with KAS Philippines?

- Civic / Political Education
- Trainings
- Dialogue Forums
- Study Tours
- Others (Kindly specify):

8. In which KAS projects has BWSC been a part of (DEPADEV, DELACSE Phase 1 or DELACSE Phase 2)?

9. What can BWSC recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX J

Interview Questionnaire **for the Initiatives for International Dialogue (IID)** **Executive Director**

1. How long have you been the executive director of IID?
2. How long has IID been working with KAS Philippines through the Institute for Autonomy and Governance (IAG)?
3. In your opinion, how did KAS Philippines through IAG contribute to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in the ASEAN?
4. What are the challenges to peacebuilding in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
5. What are the challenges to the role of non-ASEAN institutions like IID?
6. What were the problems encountered by IID in Mindanao and Philippine peacebuilding efforts in ASEAN?
7. Which among the following activities did you conduct together with KAS Philippines?
 - Civic / Political Education
 - Trainings
 - Dialogue Forums
 - Study Tours
 - Others (Kindly specify):
8. In which KAS projects has IID been a part of (DEPADEV, DELACSE Phase 1 or DELACSE Phase 2)?
9. What can IID recommend to provide other ASEAN member states with valuable lessons to aid them in peacekeeping efforts?

Note: You may use additional pages if the given space is insufficient.

Thank you very much for participating in the interview!

APPENDIX K

CONSENT FORM

1. I _____ voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
2. I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
3. I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
4. I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
5. I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
6. I understand that extracts from my interview may be quoted in research papers to be written as well as presentations in conferences and symposia.
7. I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for 12 months after the interview.
8. I understand that under freedom of information legalization I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
9. I understand that I am free to contact the person involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

*Ronna Mae A. Villanueva
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+639176891104*

Signature of research participant

Signature over printed name

Date

Ronna Mae A. Villanueva

Signature over printed name

07 January 2020

Date